

Distribution and plant availability of Cd, Pb, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions

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Abstract : The present study was conducted to evaluate the distribution and plant availability of Cd, Pb, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions. The distribution of total heavy metals and their plant availability were investigated in a metal mining area in the Hunan Province, China. Soils were partitioned into five particle-size fractions : coarse sand (> 500 μm), medium sand (125–500 μm), fine sand (50–125 μm), silt (2–50 μm) and clay (<2 μm). The most dominant elements in all size fractions at all sites are Pb and Cu followed by Cd and As. The concentration of heavy metals and metalloid in the studied soils ranged between 718–936 mg/kg : Pb, 9.625–28.352 mg/kg : Cd, 92–142 mg/kg : Cu and 42.882–74.862 mg/kg : As. Concentrations of plant available Pb (42.964–141.968 mg/kg), Cd (2.846–11.273 mg/kg), Cu (15.932–21.857 mg/kg) and As (6.954–9.251 mg/kg) in the soils were higher in the clay fraction (<2 μm). According to risk assessment code (RAC) value the studied soil revealed the following sequence : Cd > Pb > Cu > As. Cd showed a high environmental risk with the RAC value for the clay (18.216–39.761%) and silt (18.904–36.181%) of the studied soil could be considered to be dangerous to surrounding soil ecosystem. The study reflected the relative importance of the particle size fractions with respect to their contribution to metal availability. The study also revealed that the Cd, Pb, Cu and As were characteristically enriched in the fine clay particles due to higher surface area and the compositional characteristics of the fine particles.

Keywords : Heavy metal, metalloid, plant-availability, contaminated soil, particle-size soil fraction, RAC.

Introduction

Elemental composition of soil not only depends on anthropogenic and lithogenic sources but also upon the textural characteristics of the soil¹. Various grain size fractions are present in the soils and all the fractions are not equally contain same concentration. It is necessary to identify and quantify the forms in which a metal is present in the specific particle-size soil fractions to gain a more specific understanding the potential impacts of elevated levels of metals in the soils. Total metal concentration in soil is usually used as the primary pollution reference and is generally not sufficient to assess the environmental impact and thus an estimation of the bioavailable fraction is necessary. Various fractions of heavy metals are present in the soils and all the fractions are not equally avail-

able to plants^{2,3}. The most potentially toxic fraction for the plant is the plant available/bioavailable fraction. Determination of bioavailability has been mostly based on the concentration of metals present in the exchangeable/carbonate soil fraction⁴⁻⁶.

Soil can be considered a sink and also act as a source that can release metals to the surrounding environment with the capacity to transfer pollutants to the groundwater, into the food chain and into the human body⁷⁻¹⁰. Metals, being persistent in nature, may remains in soil for a long period of time are absorbed by plant roots and translocation to the foliage and edible parts^{11,12}. Accumulation of metals in different plant parts depends on the availability and chemical form of metals present in soil, their mobilization potential and variety of plant species and their

stage of maturity^{12,13}. Excessive accumulation of metals in plant tissue may induce oxidative stress by generating reactive oxygen species, which can disrupt normal physiological and biochemical functions of plants¹⁴. Hyperaccumulation of metals in crops may pose serious threat to human, who consumes crops/vegetables grown in metal contaminated areas.

Determination of bioavailable metal is a useful mean to predict the amounts of metal in soil environment readily available for the uptake in plant tissues. Thus, it is important to evaluate the bioavailability and mobility of heavy metals in granulometric fractions and to understand chemical behavior of heavy metal contaminants in soils. The objective of the present study is (i) to evaluate the effect of particle size fractions on heavy metal distribution in soil and (ii) to study the mobility and plant availability of heavy metals in different particle-size soil fractions.

Materials and methods :

Sample collection and preparation :

Surface soils were collected from 6 different regions from the contaminated sites of metal mining-smelting area; to analyze the heavy metals in granulometric fractions and to determine the phytoavailability of heavy metals (Pb, Cd and Cu) and metalloid (As) present in the soils. Soils samples (0–20 cm) were collected from the arable land of typical smelting district of Zhuzhou City, Hunan Province, China, which belongs to allitic udic ferriols and develops from the typical quaternary red clay. According to Chinese soil classification the soil of Hunan Province is red and acidic in nature¹⁵ and this region is located under the severe H₂SO₄-type acid rain pollution¹⁶. Each sample was picked out from a mixture of 3–5 subsamples. The soil samples were collected in polyethylene bags and immediately sent to the laboratory for heavy metal estimation. Soils were air-dried and sieved through a 2 mm sieve to remove large debris, stones and pebbles. Soils were partitioned into five particle-size fractions with sieve : coarse sand (> 500 μm), medium sand (125–500 μm), fine sand (50–125 μm), silt (2–50 μm) and clay (<2 μm). All glass and plastic-ware was soaked in 12% (v/v) nitric acid overnight and rinsed thoroughly with deionized

water before use.

Analytical methods :

The 1st step of sequential extraction method¹⁷ (Rauret *et al.* 1999) which operationally defines the HOAc extractable chemical form was applied to determine the phytoavailability of metals. The total metal contents determined directly (by acid digestion using a mixture of HF, HNO₃ and HClO₄) on hot plates at atmospheric pressure. For total metal analysis, dried soil sample about 0.20 g was accurately weighed and taken into a clean, dry digestion crucible and firstly digested with a solution of HF (10 mL) and concentrated HNO₃ (2 mL) to near dryness at 140 °C. Subsequently, a second addition of HF (5 mL) was made and again the mixture was evaporated to near dryness. Finally, HClO₄ (2 mL) alone was added and evaporated until the appearance of white fumes. The residue was dissolved in 1 : 1 HNO₃ (2 mL) and diluted to 50 mL¹⁸. Elemental concentrations from each particle-size soil fractions were measured using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, IRIS Intrepid II XSP, USA). Quality assurance of metal analysis was assured through the analysis of SRM for soil obtained from China National Center for Standard Reference Materials (Soil : GBW-08303) and standard reference solution in the process of analysis in order to check the accuracy and precision.

Results and discussion

Distribution of plant-available metals in particle size fractions :

To determine the phytoavailability of heavy metals, the 1st step of mBCR¹⁷ (Rauret *et al.* 1999) was applied in this study, and the concentration of Pb, Cd, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions were shown in Table 1. The toxicity and bioavailability of heavy metals in soils is mainly dependent on its chemical speciation rather than its total concentrations in the soils. From the study it was observed that the extractable amounts Pb were high in the clay fraction. Concentrations of extractable Pb (42.964–141.968 mg/kg), Cd (2.846–11.273 mg/kg), Cu (15.932–21.857 mg/kg) and As (6.954–9.251 mg/kg) in the soils were

Table 1. Concentration (mg/kg) of plant available Pb, Cd, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions

Sites	Fraction	Pb	Cd	Cu	As	Sites	Fraction	Pb	Cd	Cu	As
S-1	<2	109.241	10.124	20.151	6.954	S-4	<2	42.964	2.846	7.942	9.251
	2-50	94.943	8.668	17.594	5.645		2-50	61.221	3.354	9.719	7.969
	50-125	77.452	6.451	15.524	4.558		50-125	69.149	5.848	12.157	7.145
	125-500	72.154	5.249	11.532	3.986		125-500	84.351	7.112	17.186	5.347
	>500	68.328	3.552	9.154	3.152		>500	97.276	8.639	21.174	5.151
S-2	<2	98.392	9.174	18.634	7.276	S-5	<2	141.968	11.273	21.857	7.697
	2-50	90.521	7.845	15.837	5.814		2-50	118.741	8.247	18.961	6.773
	50-125	83.327	7.119	14.462	5.247		50-125	107.432	7.154	15.762	4.689
	125-500	71.431	5.293	10.428	3.159		125-500	96.814	5.573	7.884	3.985
	>500	57.224	4.558	9.531	1.985		>500	82.923	4.962	7.583	2.896
S-3	<2	132.412	6.883	16.637	7.415	S-6	<2	109.761	7.752	15.932	7.346
	2-50	104.635	5.579	15.134	6.374		2-50	85.372	5.874	14.135	6.148
	50-125	95.297	4.865	10.876	5.486		50-125	77.629	4.627	12.634	4.957
	125-500	83.862	4.257	8.941	4.974		125-500	69.822	2.943	10.832	3.927
	>500	69.216	2.974	7.546	2.324		>500	51.426	2.254	8.649	1.984

higher in the clay fraction (<2 μm). Silt fraction also contain higher level of Pb (61.221–118.741 mg/kg), Cd (3.354–8.668 mg/kg), Cu (14.135–18.961 mg/kg) and As (5.645–7.969 mg/kg) than the other coarser fractions. The concentrations of phytoavailable heavy metals in different size classes demonstrated higher accumulation in finer fractions, and the metals mainly accumulated in the fractions of clay and silt. The metals and metalloid were characteristically enriched in the fine particles due to higher surface area and the compositional characteristics of the fine particles. Among the studied fractions the coarse sand (>500 μm) contains low concentration of extractable Pb (51.426–97.276 mg/kg), Cd (2.254–8.639 mg/kg), Cu (7.546–9.531 mg/kg) and As (1.984–5.151 mg/kg). The elevated level of extractable metals was observed at the site S-5 may be due to the recent input of these elements. The study revealed that finer soil particles tend to show higher concentrations of heavy metals though it is not applicable in all the sites and also in all the metals. However, in comparison to other sites, the site S-4 showed high concentrations of most of the metals in the coarser fraction except for As. This behavior could be due to the process of treatment of the ore, where biggest particles remain enriched with metals probably because they contain several minerals. According to Hernandez *et al.*

(2003)¹⁹ the bioavailability, mobility, and activity of soil heavy metals in the field were greatly affected by acid deposition. Hunan Province, in China is located in the center area of acid deposition. This may be due to the one of the causes of high level of extractable metals in the study area.

Total metal content and enrichment factor of heavy metals in soil fractions :

The total metal concentrations and enrichment factor of heavy metals and metalloid in different particle-size soil fractions were represented in Table 2. The concentrations of Pb, Cd, Cu and As in the studied region ranged from 718–936 mg/kg, 9.625–28.352 mg/kg, 92–142 mg/kg and 42.882–74.862 mg/kg respectively. The concentrations of total metal concentration in different size fractions demonstrated higher accumulation in finer fractions. Relatively higher concentration of studied metals were observed in the clay fraction (<2 μm), where the Pb, Cd, Cu and As concentration ranged from 718–936 mg/kg, 15.624–28.352 mg/kg, 130–142 mg/kg and 62.327–74.862 mg/kg respectively. The coarse sand (>500 μm) fraction contains low concentration of total Pb (720–889 mg/kg), Cd (9.625–24.512 mg/kg), Cu (92–110 mg/kg) and As (42.882–53.145 mg/kg). The study revealed that the heavy metals were not homogeneously distributed among the various particle fractions, sug-

Table 2. Total metal concentrations (mg/kg) and enrichment factors of Pb, Cd, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions

Sites	Fraction	Pb		Cd		Cu		As	
		Conc.	EF	Conc.	EF	Conc.	EF	Conc.	EF
S-1	<2	852	28.687	26.341	202.623	136	4.982	62.327	3.970
	2-50	807	27.172	23.957	184.285	124	4.542	56.326	3.588
	50-125	771	25.960	20.334	156.415	120	4.396	51.541	3.283
	125-500	743	25.017	19.645	151.115	116	4.249	47.254	3.010
	>500	724	24.377	17.623	135.562	110	4.029	43.532	2.773
S-2	<2	872	29.360	25.934	199.492	131	4.799	64.634	4.117
	2-50	809	27.239	23.241	178.777	122	4.469	58.596	3.732
	50-125	775	26.094	21.172	162.862	116	4.249	55.328	3.524
	125-500	741	24.949	18.693	143.792	112	4.103	50.341	3.206
	>500	720	24.242	16.854	129.646	107	3.919	46.345	2.952
S-3	<2	912	30.707	22.637	174.131	130	4.762	68.171	4.342
	2-50	849	28.586	20.551	158.085	120	4.396	61.289	3.904
	50-125	821	27.643	18.342	141.092	115	4.212	58.394	3.719
	125-500	805	27.104	17.648	135.754	104	3.810	54.622	3.479
	>500	786	26.465	14.527	111.746	95	3.480	51.674	3.291
S-4	<2	718	24.175	15.624	120.185	102	3.736	74.862	4.768
	2-50	727	24.478	17.742	136.477	114	4.176	69.425	4.422
	50-125	741	24.949	18.154	139.646	122	4.469	64.774	4.126
	125-500	863	29.057	20.329	156.377	133	4.872	59.682	3.801
	>500	889	29.933	24.512	188.554	142	5.201	53.145	3.385
S-5	<2	936	31.515	28.352	218.092	132	4.835	63.462	4.042
	2-50	919	30.943	24.312	187.015	119	4.359	59.226	3.772
	50-125	891	30.000	22.749	174.992	110	4.029	53.374	3.400
	125-500	873	29.394	20.739	159.531	99	3.626	49.657	3.163
	>500	847	28.519	19.328	148.677	92	3.370	42.882	2.731
S-6	<2	907	30.539	20.421	157.085	140	5.128	72.167	4.597
	2-50	879	29.596	17.457	134.285	131	4.799	61.951	3.946
	50-125	853	28.721	15.854	121.954	122	4.469	56.647	3.608
	125-500	831	27.980	11.612	89.323	114	4.176	52.823	3.365
	>500	812	27.340	9.625	74.038	107	3.919	48.322	3.078

gesting the influence of sediment texture on the partitioning of heavy metals. Soils polluted by mining and metal smelting activities and many sites of ancient industrial activity continue to have very high levels of heavy metals in the soils²⁰⁻²⁶. Total concentration of heavy metals and metalloid in the contaminated soils that were studied reflects a difference in the degree of soil contamination. This result suggested that the soils were extensively polluted with hazardous metals in the studied area due to mining and metal smelting activities. The concentration of Cu in the studied soil

did not exceed the standard value (400 mg/kg) (GB 15618-1995)²⁷. The metals and metalloid concentrations in all the sampling sites were exceeded the corresponding background values (500, 1.0 and 40 mg/kg for Pb, Cd and As, respectively) of the Soil Environmental Quality Standard in China (GB 15618-1995)²⁷.

To evaluate the magnitude of contaminants in the soil environment, normalized enrichment factors (EF) were computed on the basis of standardization of a measured element against a reference element. This

is determined by the equation : $EF = (M/X) \text{ sample} / (M/X) \text{ background}$, where M is the measured concentration of the element in the soil, X is the selected normalize (reference metal) and (M/X) sample and (M/X) background are the ratios of target metal and the normalizer in the interest and background soils, respectively. Fe was chosen as the element for normalization as because anthropogenic sources are small compared to natural sources²⁸. Average shale values of Fe were used as the reference element which was taken from Turekian and Wedepohl (1961)²⁹. A five-category ranking system was recognized on the basis of the enrichment factor : $EF < 2$ deficiencies to minimal enrichment, $EF = 2-5$ moderate enrichment, $EF = 5-20$ significant enrichment, $EF = 20-40$ very high enrichment and $EF > 40$ extremely high enrichment^{30,31}. Compared to the coarser particles the metals were enriched in the finer particles. The calculated results (Table 2) showed that Cd and Pb showed the highest EF values, ranged from 24.175–31.515 and 74.038–218.0924, respectively. Relatively lower EF values were obtained for Cu and As, ranged from of 3.370–5.201 and 2.731–4.768, respectively. The enrichment factors of metals indicated that clay fraction ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$) having extremely high enrichment of Cd and very high enrichment of Pb while Cu and As are moderately enriched. Overall EF of the studied

metals in the surface soils indicating anthropogenic source of contamination i.e. smelting waste contamination prevailing in the study area. Heavy metals tended to accumulate in the fine fractions, which can be indicated more clearly by the enrichment factors.

Risk assessment code (RAC) :

The risk assessment code (RAC) classification, indicates the potential ecotoxicological risk, which is based on the percentage of metal in the carbonate and exchangeable fractions was used to assess the bioavailability of metals in soils according to the extracted-metals from the step 1 of BCR (Community Bureau of Reference sequential extraction procedure)³². The RAC values of Pb, Cd, Cu and As were represented in the Table 3. The design formula is as follows : $RAC = \frac{\text{the amount of F1}}{\text{the total concentrations}} \times 100\%$. There is considered to be no risk when the F1 BCR fraction is $< 1\%$, a low risk for a range of 1–10%, a medium risk for a range of 11–30%, a high risk from 31 to 50% and a very high risk for F1 percentages $> 50\%$ ³³. Cd showed a high environmental risk with the RAC value for the clay (18.216–39.761%) and silt (18.904–36.181%) of the studied soil could be considered to be dangerous to surrounding soil ecosystem. In some sites fine sand (50–125 μm) also exhibit high RAC value ($> 30\%$) and could be considered as dangerous to surrounding

Table 3. Risk assessment code values (%) of Pb, Cd, Cu and As in different particle-size soil fractions

Sites	Fraction	Pb	Cd	Cu	As	Sites	Fraction	Pb	Cd	Cu	As
S-1	<2	12.822	38.434	14.817	11.157	S-4	<2	5.984	18.216	7.786	12.357
	2-50	11.765	36.181	14.189	10.022		2-50	8.421	18.904	8.525	11.479
	50-125	10.046	31.725	12.937	8.843		50-125	9.332	32.213	9.965	11.031
	125-500	9.711	26.719	9.941	8.435		125-500	9.774	34.985	12.922	8.959
	>500	9.438	20.155	8.322	7.241		>500	10.942	35.244	14.911	9.692
S-2	<2	11.283	35.374	14.224	11.257	S-5	<2	15.168	39.761	16.558	12.129
	2-50	11.189	33.755	12.981	9.922		2-50	12.921	33.922	15.934	11.436
	50-125	10.752	33.625	12.467	9.483		50-125	12.057	31.448	14.329	8.785
	125-500	9.640	28.315	9.311	6.275		125-500	11.090	26.872	7.964	8.025
	>500	7.948	27.044	8.907	4.283		>500	9.790	25.673	8.242	6.753
S-3	<2	14.519	30.406	12.798	10.877	S-6	<2	12.102	37.961	11.380	10.179
	2-50	12.324	27.147	12.612	10.400		2-50	9.712	33.648	10.790	9.924
	50-125	11.607	26.524	9.457	9.395		50-125	9.101	29.185	10.356	8.751
	125-500	10.418	24.122	8.597	9.106		125-500	8.402	25.344	9.502	7.434
	>500	8.806	20.472	7.943	4.497		>500	6.333	23.418	8.083	4.106

soil ecosystem. Low or medium environmental risks were represented for Cu and As with ranged from 7.786–16.558% and 4.106–12.357% respectively. The obtained overall RAC values for Pb (5.984–15.68%) showed medium environmental risk though, under changing environmental conditions they may be released back to the surrounding soil environment. The study revealed that the studied metals in clay and silt fraction can easily enter the food-chain and bring possible ecotoxicological risk to organisms living in soils according to the risk assessment code.

Conclusions

The concentrations of phytoavailable heavy metals in different size classes demonstrated higher accumulation in finer fractions, and the metals mainly accumulated in the fractions of clay and silt. Among the analyzed heavy metals and metalloid, Cd and Pb are the most dominant elements in all size fractions at all sites, followed by Cu and As. The study revealed that finer soil particles tend to show higher concentrations of heavy metals though it is not applicable in all the sites and also in all the metals. Cd, Pb, Cu and As were characteristically enriched in the fine particles due to higher surface area and the compositional characteristics of the fine particles. The higher concentrations of the metals in most of the particle size fractions and higher increment in the coarser particles, indicating a lower recovery of the metals during the treatment of ore. This result suggested that the soils were extensively polluted with hazardous metals in the studied area. Heavy metals tended to accumulate in the fine fractions, which can be indicated more clearly by the enrichment factors. The study revealed that the studied metals and metalloid in clay and silt fraction having higher RAC values, can easily enter into the food-chain and may bring possible ecotoxicological risk to organisms living in soils.

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